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Management system for regulatory requirements applicable to environmentally classified industrial facilities

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Abstract

We propose to present an approach to managing major industrial risks to the environment that we developed at Seveso high threshold sites for the storage of hydrocarbons, the manufacture of fertilisers or pyrotechnics, and at dams. The basic idea behind this approach is that these sites must demonstrate their ability to manage major risks, but that the risk analyses prove nothing until proof is provided of the truth of their premises, the logical validity of their arguments, the realism of their conclusions, and the effective implementation of the modelled risk control measures and tasks. Demonstrating risk control is therefore an ongoing process based on piloting and monitoring the correspondence between these items and the reality of industrial processes and their environments. Risk assessments are the basis, but not the complete demonstration. Is this a new idea? Certainly not. But what does seem new to us, and what we would like to present, is the risk management approach that we have built around this simple idea. The difficulty we have faced in achieving this is the implementation of a flexible digital platform, made necessary by the quantity and diversity of the data, methods, models, and regulatory requirements to be managed, and moreover by the number and diversity of the stakeholders. The design of the database came up against a major scientific obstacle, that of the diversity of representations of the various risk management stakeholders, and therefore of the different types of process for developing or using all these data, methods, models, and regulatory requirements; a source of richness but also of misunderstanding, mistrust and, ultimately, under certain conditions, of increased risk. This is the problem of the silos of expertise and disciplines in the face of the need for distributed/shared cognition to build up one database around a single and holistic risk model (a common operational picture). We would like to present the stages of our method and our Web IT tools.

1. Introduction

For ten years, Vassishtasai RAMANY, environmental manager and then deputy director of SNOI (the French part of NATO's oil pipeline network in Central Europe), Christophe COLL, environmental engineer specialising in risk assessment at Dekra Industrial, and Emmanuel PLOT, philosopher specialising in major risk management systems and IT at INERIS, worked closely together to design a method supported by IT tools to provide the transparency needed to manage the major risks for SNOI's network of 14 oil depots. Previously, Emmanuel PLOT had designed a model of a good organisation for managing major risks (Plot, E., 2007), an integrated risk and critical task model for designing simulations in virtual environments (Plot 2010), and during the ten years of the SNOI project, he has been working on the SNOI method also with several colleagues, first as part of the European Tosca project (Leva, C., 2019), then with other industrial partners. Frederic Baudequin of Interactive, a French company, provided the IT foundation and continuous support.

The starting point is the need to comply with environmental regulations. It is difficult, because there is a profusion of themes (water, soil and subsoil, air, waste, noise, accidental and chronic risks, planning requirements or exemption requests, ageing monitoring) and applicable texts that are constantly evolving: decrees (ministerial, prefectural, municipal), agreements (collective or between two companies), administrative regulations (internal regulations, internal charters, employment or commercial contracts), professional guides) and, linked to this, numerous risk studies published in separate reports several hundred pages long. The Environment Code itself, which is supposed to provide a general framework, is extremely

difficult to read, and its links with other codes, such as the Town Planning Code, are no easier to decipher (Morel, C., 2018). We have no reason to complain about the number of standards. They have their *raison d'être*. But it is so difficult to deal with the multiplicity of regulatory aspects, the heterogeneity of deadlines and expectations, and the diversity of knowledge management cycles to be taken into account. The method consists of supporting the interpretation of the law, in order to achieve its strict application.

For this, risk analysis is the key, because they enable regulations to be interpreted in the light of the realities on the ground, they eliminate arbitrary decisions, and they organize cooperation to understand, prioritize and resolve problems. But risk analyses are not enough, because they prove nothing. Rather, they should be seen as promises. They are not demonstrations in the strict sense of the term. They must be supplemented by protocols designed to prove that they are in line with reality and that they remain so over time. These protocols take up the results of the risk analyses and verify their veracity, so that they are, strictly speaking, demonstrations of risk control. The introduction and dynamic monitoring of these protocols make risk management organizations more transparent and easier to manage (Leva, C., 2015). This is what the method is all about.

2. Presentation of the method

2.1 Step 1: List all the fundamental problems to be solved

The first step is to draw up a systematic list of all the fundamental issues that need to be addressed. What is the basis for this list? The answer that immediately springs to mind is the Environmental Code. It's a good idea, but difficult to put into practice. Because the Environment Code is huge. It covers so many subjects and so many subtleties. It would require an army of specialists. It's not realistic for an operator. It's not their job. The pragmatic solution chosen by the SNOI was to prefer to rely on prefectural operating authorization decrees. Aren't these supposed to include all the requirements established in accordance with the Environmental Code and the industrial processes studied in the risk analyses? In other words, aren't they the interface between the legal system and the reality on the ground? Wouldn't this be an excellent basis for avoiding any blind spots in terms of ICPE regulations? The work has already been done by the inspectorate. Valuable work on which operators can rely.

2.2 Step 2: Asking the right questions

Operating license requirements must be understood to be complied with. They cannot be applied automatically. First and foremost, it is important to identify the purpose of the requirement: why was it written in the first place? Then we need to think about the best ways of achieving it. It seems appropriate to consider these regulations as questions put to the operator, of the type: 'you, the operator, how do you go about complying with this or that? The first thing to do, then, is to 'slice and dice' the texts of the decrees to extract the list of questions that need to be answered.

2.3 Step 3: Answer

2.3.1 Clarifying the issues raised by the specifications

In many cases, it is necessary to interpret the requirements by delving into the risk analyses to which they refer, to fully understand them. The questions then become clearer:

- How can a given level of confidence be maintained in each barrier?
- How can we guarantee the validity of the estimated frequency of a given initiating event under a given condition?
- How can we guarantee that a given hazard potential will not be exceeded? How can we control the parameters considered in modelling a given hazardous event (pressure, temperature, etc.)?
- How can we ensure control of the parameters linked to certain exclusions in each part of a given risk analysis, or to potential changes in the issues at stake that are likely to have an impact on the estimate of severity?

In addition, very often the requirements are written in such a way that important aspects of the questions are not immediately understandable. In this case, the requirements need to be supplemented. For example, probabilistic aspects tend to disappear from operating license requirements when they require the implementation of a particular barrier without reference to acceptance of its probability of failure under stress, or to the safety architecture in which it fits. In addition, reference to the criticality of the hazardous phenomena affected by any failure of this barrier is generally omitted. This is particularly problematic when the failure of this barrier, given the frequencies of initiating events and other safety barriers, and given the importance of the issues at stake, degrades the level of risk control without making it unacceptable. Ultimately, risk management must systematically be based on an analysis of the criticality of accident scenarios. This criticality is dynamic (Amalberti, R., 1996). It changes according to several parameters (state of barriers, etc.), which makes it particularly complex to manage. By incorporating these parameters into a model, efforts can be concentrated on risk management and on the necessary continuous updating of operator representations (Amalberti, R. 1996).

2.3.2 Defining doctrines and critical tasks

The resulting questions are posed one by one to the organization. What are we doing about it? What are we doing about it? Is it sufficient? Satisfactory? Do we need to improve? The answers are written in the form of doctrines, i.e., management rules adapted to the organization in question, to be implemented to answer the questions. This is the structure of an organization manual.

As in any organization, these rules are translated into tasks, which are the subject of various procedures, instructions, or operating methods. These tasks can be described as critical. The doctrine is the most general level of organization, the task the most detailed. Tasks define the objectives that operators must achieve to control risks and demonstrate this control. They correspond to the definition of a job to be carried out, and to the prescribed and formal description of the actions to be carried out. A critical task is the description of an action whose failure reduces the level of risk control.

Doctrines and tasks must be thought out, designed, and developed with those who will be responsible for them, with their references, their good practices, and their cultures (at the risk of being unrealistic), and then assumed by Management. It is not up to the inspector to prescribe the means that the manufacturer must implement. That is not his role. He can, however, adopt the operator's good practices and include them in his instructions.

The challenge is obviously to deal with as many requirements as possible with as few doctrines and tasks as possible.

2.3.3 By carrying out risk analyses

Doctrines refer (or should refer) to the risk analyses that precede or extend them, just as regulatory requirements refer to or require risk analyses. These analyses make it possible to interpret regulations in the light of the realities on the ground, eliminate arbitrary decisions and organize cooperation to understand, prioritize and resolve problems.

This is why critical tasks:

- require risk analyses to be carried out,
- control:
 - the realism of their premises (based on the best available data, or the best available scientific knowledge or expertise),
 - the logical validity of their arguments (based on methodological references),
 - the realism of their conclusions (based on indicators that are as independent as possible of the arguments),
 - the effective implementation of risk control measures.

When the problems are simple, known, controlled and generic, these analyses are implicit and therefore do not need to be formalized. They are obvious and accepted by everyone. On the other hand, when the problems are complicated, poorly understood, and specific, they may be imposed on the operator by regulations or decided voluntarily. They are not opposed to regulations or doctrines but precede or specify them: they clarify questions and provide answers.

2.3.4 By establishing demonstration protocols that extend the risk analyses

2.3.4.1 Checking premises

These risk analyses are based on premises that need to be verified (Peschard I., et al, 2022). The aim is to check that reality corresponds to the facts considered by these analyses. This is an ongoing process because reality is always in flux. In practice, these verifications are carried out by means of initial or additional studies, each time calling on the expertise of specialists in the realities under consideration: laboratory tests, controls, and various studies. Of course, these complementary analyses generally build on each other.

The premises are validated on the basis of their consistency and complementarity. For example, the validity of a measure to monitor the presence of environmentally hazardous substances in the water of a piezometer located downstream of a site presupposes the coordinated validity of:

- an analysis specifying the safety functions to be ensured (in particular the type of substance to be monitored),
- a hydrogeological study to define the functional specifications of the piezometers,
- an engineering file to check compliance with these specifications in the field,
- the file for each piezometer, which specifies the operating procedure to be followed for the readings (frequency, parameters, and practices to be observed),
- the organization of the readings (who, what equipment and what skills),
- the organization of laboratory analyses,
- the skills of the experts who will read and interpret the results from a risk perspective.

2.3.4.2 Checking the logical validity of arguments

Checking the logical validity of arguments is traditionally the 'paper' work of third-party experts or inspectors. They check the logical rigour of the arguments and compliance with the principles defined in the reference methodological guides, such as the INERIS Omega. But the more voluminous the analyses, the more delicate the task. It is not easy to find the logic of the reasoning in hundreds of pages of PDF files. The documents often exceed 1000 pages (with their appendices), and often refer to other studies. It should also be noted that the referential integrity of proposals is all the more difficult to establish as their formulation or conception changes during the drafting process. It is difficult to be perfectly consistent when writing voluminous studies over several months, if only in the formulation of proposals. Even more so when the initial data - the premises - provided to the analysts on the processes and their environment are clarified or simply modified during the analysis, and whole sections of the argument must be reworked afterwards.

2.3.4.3 Checking conclusions

In addition to checking the premises and the rigour of the argument, it is necessary to verify, as far as possible, the realism of the results. This can be done either by tracking down aberrant conclusions, or by relying on indicators that are as independent as possible of the argumentative logic. Note that this is easier for the risks of chronic emissions of pollutants, but more difficult, if not impossible, for major accident scenarios which, by definition, are simply possible and therefore undetectable or apprehensible in reality, independently of a model.

2.3.4.4 Checking the implementation of risk control measures

In addition to the above checks, which question the reliability and incompleteness of the demonstrations, the operational conclusions of the risk analyses must be drawn by implementing the measures identified to guarantee a level of control that is acceptable from the regulatory point of view.

It should be noted that this requirement can be considered as a sub-category of the premises control work. These measures make it possible to ensure that the risk studies correspond to the reality of the installations. The premises approach can be seen as simply more encompassing in that it also raises questions about the reliability and potentially incomplete nature of the elements on which the arguments justifying the importance of these measures are based.

2.3.4.5 By carrying out critical tasks

These protocols complete the system for answering questions raised by regulatory requirements. They complete

the demonstration of risk control. They are made up of tasks or combinations of tasks linked together by dependency relationships. These tasks may be external to operational tasks, or intrinsically linked to production, maintenance, or logistics. They include:

- Tasks for controlling precise parameters, defined to ensure the ongoing validity of the premises of risk analyses concerning:
 - exclusions (including hazard potential threshold),
 - frequencies of initiating events
 - confidence level of barriers
 - modelling assumptions
 - severity of potential accidents.
- Or tasks that require additional analysis to refine the specifications of other tasks.
- Or tasks involving checking the risk analysis procedures themselves: checking the conditions under which these analyses are carried out or the methods used.
- Or tasks to check that the conclusions of the risk analysis are realistic (when they are chronic).

These tasks can be directly linked to the doctrines when the risk analyses are not formalized because the subject is simple, known and mastered.

The resources allocated to these tasks are managed:

- Management of the distribution of roles and responsibilities for carrying out the tasks
- Skills management
- Equipment management
- Management of methods, procedures, guides, operating modes, or instructions
- Management of task objective updates

These tasks are also associated with records that provide proof that they have been carried out correctly or that the desired results have been achieved.

2.3.4.6 By recording these tasks as evidence

Critical tasks are recorded. Some of these records can be used as evidence. These records, this evidence, are necessarily based on the choice of certain parameters, which are limited, considered to be genuinely relevant and likely to change over time. Not everything can be controlled or proven. We must admit this pragmatically, without complexes, and try to make relevant and strategic choices, considering the costs/benefits in determining these parameters. These choices are up for discussion. They must be debatable, and discussed until they appear to be the most relevant, without discussion, and are validated by the COPIL.

These parameters must be precisely associated with the objectives and resources that they enable to be monitored. Otherwise, there can be no reflection on the relevance of their choice and use, and on the limits of their validity. We need to be able to trace parameters back to doctrines and regulatory requirements. The simplest way of doing this is to consider these parameters as records linked to critical tasks. In this way, we know how they are considered, how the data is produced, by whom and under what conditions. In this way, the evidence appears as compilations (or aggregations), at the level of the doctrines, of the records of critical tasks.

It should also be noted that:

- Evidence (and the parameters on which it is based) must be open to challenge and may have only temporary validity, justified by changes in operations or advances in scientific or technical knowledge.
- Evidence can be introduced gradually, according to an order of priority to be established. It takes time to involve people and time to discuss choices, to experiment when problems are new, to find resources, and then time to implement them. It is then that the inspector, lawyer, and judge can assess the bona fides of what has been put in place.

- Evidence is produced for the operator before it is produced for the inspector. The operator wants to know whether what he has asked his organization to do is being done properly. This is a good investment rationale, which builds confidence.
- As far as possible, the proof should not represent a new effort for the organization. Ideally, it should be based on existing practices, such as maintenance software. Maintenance data is already reliable. It already exists. Using it costs nothing (or very little!).
- The evidence can:
 - be widely tested by the profession, or be custom designed,
 - refers to short cycles of data collection (every second, for example) or long cycles (every ten years).
- Evidence must be adapted to the kinetics of the phenomena and the time required to intervene.

2.3.4.7 By periodically recalculating the criticality of hazardous phenomena

A risk analysis is an estimate of the probability of occurrence of possible hazardous phenomena in the future, based on current knowledge of past events. Ongoing work on critical tasks enables us to update our knowledge of exclusions, frequencies of triggering events, barriers, the modelling of hazardous phenomena and the sensitivity of the issues at stake, and therefore to periodically redo the calculations. This regular review of analyses provides a solid basis for risk management.

2.4 Step 4: Management

2.4.1 Based on risk management demonstration protocols

Nothing is set in stone, because the reality of an industrial plants is constantly evolving: staff turnover, changes to processes or the environment, ageing facilities, change of supplier, etc. The risk management organization is based on realities that are constantly changing. The greater the risks, the greater the need for precision, and the more these changes, however small they may appear, can profoundly alter the level of risk control, and must be considered by the organization.

These changes cannot lead to a revision of the regulatory requirements or of the risk analyses, but only of the protocols for demonstrating risk control, i.e., the ability to carry out the critical tasks, which are responsible for justifying or verifying the premises, arguments, or conclusions of the risk analyses.

Management must therefore be based on demonstration protocols, to check, on a cyclical basis, that they are still in place and that responses to regulatory requirements are being implemented, in line with the reality on the ground.

2.4.2 With the help of a steering committee

There are no technical choices in terms of processes, then doctrines and risk analyses, then organizational investments, then validation by the steering committee: the choices must be analyzed, taking into account risks, processes and organizational capabilities, and steered by the steering committee.

This requires a committed and well-trained management team, which, without going into the technical details, has an overview of the possible solutions to decide whether or not to invest.

Worth noting:

- The steering committee meets regularly, every six months, and is chaired by the director.
- The steering committee focuses on unresolved problems.
- The steering committee is not the place where problems are discovered, but where solutions are decided. This means that project-based organizations need to be set up before the steering committee meetings, which need to be prepared, typically according to the following cycle:
 - At the beginning of the six-month period, the organizations dedicated to implementing the actions decided at the previous steering committee must be designed.
 - One month before a steering committee meeting, the subjects to be dealt with should be specified, based on the provisional timetable, regulatory changes, difficulties encountered, or results obtained under the actions decided on.
- The steering committee presentations should be designed to help management make decisions:

- Common topics should be grouped together and, as far as possible, a common thread should be found between the topics.
- The presentations should be reviewed by the action leaders, at least the day before, to resolve any problems that can be dealt with without a management decision.
- The Director takes note of and accepts the decisions taken and the action plan, which becomes a guideline for everyone.
- The CR is validated by everyone. Once finalized, it becomes a basic tool for coordination between the steering committees.

2.4.3 By establishing priorities

2.4.3.1 Depending on the kinetics and criticality of the risk

Not all problems have the same importance, because they do not affect the kinetics and criticality of hazardous phenomena in the same way. It is rational to adjust the allocation of the organization's resources according to these two parameters. This adjustment is based on analyses. The organization designs its specifications on the basis of risk analyses and their updates.

2.4.3.2 According to the organisation's capabilities

Another prioritization criterion relates to the difficulty for an organization to implement a task. There are several possible scenarios.

Case 1: The solution is known. This is the vast majority of cases. It must be deployed, even if it is difficult to implement, as in the case of:

- Some accident scenarios are so serious that there are still doubts about the means of controlling them, even though they have already been tried and tested, are known, controlled, and implemented by the organization.
- There is a need for standardization, because certain practices are not mastered across an entire site or across all sites.
- Problems that are well known and under control need to be dealt with quickly, as a matter of priority.

We need to apply the principle of subsidiarity.

Case 2: the solution has not been fully studied, tested and validated. We need to take the time to explore one or more satisfactory solutions, using an experimental approach, and carry out additional analyses before making a decision, if necessary by the steering committee.

Case 3: the possible solutions involve uncontrolled practices. This is a completely different case. Using an experimental approach, the solutions will have to be classified and analyzed, then their design and implementation will have to be closely monitored, tested, and evaluated. This will result in investment programs to be decided by the steering committee.

2.4.3.3 According to steering capacity

It is not possible to discuss all the unresolved issues that fall within the remit of a COPIL at the same time. Prioritized issues are dealt with over time. Some problems can be dealt with over the course of several meetings, or even several years. There is therefore an agreed schedule for dealing with problems in the steering committee, and adjustments to this schedule. Everyone is aware of the schedule, which is communicated to the inspectorate and controlled by management. Rushing to deal with problems could lead to even bigger problems.

3. IT tools

The method involves constructing a demonstration of the control of major risks. This is based on steps involving the manipulation, articulation and re-articulation of knowledge: the data from the risk analysis is restructured around accident scenarios (events and barriers); these scenarios are redesigned so that the players in the field can position their critical tasks within them; the latter are described in terms of resources; the management of these

resources is described by support, monitoring and audit processes; the whole process is dynamically controlled on the basis of evidence.

It seems virtually impossible to ensure the fluid management of all this knowledge and, above all, its links within a risk control demonstration without using a computer ontology (Bachimont B., 2007) and therefore a database. This is why the method is computerized (Aneziris O., 2019).

The software solution has been designed to enable several players to work together, each from their own point of view, on the same data and the same model. The solution is therefore not rigid software, with a set of pre-established screens, but an ultra-flexible development platform (Plot, 2022 & 2023), with screens tailored to each player (in a DevOps approach). First, the tool enables us to reach everyone where they are, by adapting to their needs and requirements, to the vision they have of their company, to the specificities linked to their history, their working environment, and so on. Then the tool offers new perspectives and opportunities. It then supports changes in practices, requirements, and visions, while ensuring the overall coherence of the organization. The heuristic is that of trial and error with all the players, around a methodology and a stable, robust digital structure (the only way to ensure overall consistency, manage changes and historical data, and guarantee permanent data control).

The solution offers:

- A common core, a deep methodological and IT layer, dedicated to the consistent management of risk analysis data, critical tasks, and processes,
- A set of resources for developing real-time workflows, data entry forms, data management screens, dashboards, and customized reporting systems, specifically tailored to the needs of each organization. These developments re-use secure software components that have already been designed and tested, enabling rapid development by focusing solely on the needs of the business and avoiding the risk of bugs.

This IT system has been specifically designed for the implementation and management of risk management systems.

4. Conclusion

It is important to be wary of simplistic approaches that can be summed up by the following statements we sometimes hear from manufacturers: 'We have taken all environmental requirements into account in our procedures, we apply our procedures 100%, and if there is a problem, we trace it and solve it; so we are good; and moreover, we have never had a notable incident or accident'. The problems with this approach are as follows:

- Procedures are often incomplete, complex, and not always applied.
- Incidents or near-accidents are recurrent on the sites.
- This formulation is tantamount to asking the person who wants to check to redo all the work:
 - list all the requirements arising from the operating license and risk studies,
 - check that they have all been identified and considered in the doctrines and tasks that are important for the environment.
 - check that they have been incorporated into operators' procedures, instructions, or operating methods.
 - check that these tasks are carried out by competent personnel (trained and assessed)
 - monitors their effectiveness using appropriate parameters.

This simplistic approach limits the scope for reflection on the real level of risk management within the organization. It means closing our eyes and not giving ourselves the means to check our own mistakes in designing our risk management system.

In contrast, the method presented in this document is specifically designed to organize the conditions for transparency which help to define the priority of actions thanks to a holistic demonstration of the effective level of risk of industrial installations and processes. The aim is to enable criticism, reflexivity, questioning and therefore improvement.

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